

Kinetics and Mechanism of Osmium Tetroxide Catalysed Oxidation of Benzoin and its Derivatives by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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The kinetics of oxidation of benzoin and four substituted benzoin by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in the presence of osmium tetroxide as catalyst have been investigated in t-butanol-water mixture at constant ionic strength. The rates of the reactions are found to be first order in [substrate], [alkali] and [catalyst], but zero order in [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. The rates of the reactions decrease with the decrease in the dielectric constant and increase with the increase in ionic strength of the medium. The mechanism involves the formation of an intermediate complex between the enolate and osmium tetroxide, which rapidly decomposes followed by a fast reaction between the reduced osmium species and hexacyanoferrate(III). This is consistent with the results obtained.

IN continuation of our earlier work on the kinetics of oxidation of aromatic ketones¹, pyridinium salts² and chalcones³ by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), we report the kinetics of osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of benzoin (keto alcohol) by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). The mechanism of oxidation depends on the catalyst, osmium tetroxide and the exact role of the osmium tetroxide in the oxidation of benzoin has not yet been shown, and this prompted us to investigate the osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of benzoin by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). In the absence of the catalyst, the reaction is extremely slow or does not proceed at all.

Experimental

Benzoin was prepared and purified by the reported⁴ method. Ethanol, potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), potassium chloride and potassium hydroxide were of AnalaR reagents. A 0.004 M solution of osmium tetroxide (Johnson Mathey) was prepared by dissolving a known weight of the sample in KOH solution (0.05 M). Dilution was made with triple-distilled water and the ionic strength adjusted with potassium chloride.

Kinetic measurement: The progress of the reaction in aqueous ethanol at the desired temperature was followed by withdrawing aliquots of the reaction mixture at known intervals of time and estimating the amount of hexacyanoferrate(II) formed during the reaction by titrating against standard solution of ceric salt using ferrion as indicator. The standard zero order rate constants (k_0) reported are the average values of duplicate runs. Oxidation of the solvent did not occur under the conditions employed.

Stoichiometry: The reaction was carried out using a known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) at 30° and the unconsumed oxidant determined as described above. The results showed that 1 mol of benzoin required 2 mol of hexacyanoferrate(III) indicating the stoichiometry to be 1 : 2. Benzil was found to be the product of oxidation. The pure product was characterised (ir, m.m.p.) as benzil, m.p. 96°.

Rate laws: The reaction is zero order in [hexacyanoferrate(III)] as shown by the constant values of k_0 over a ten-fold variation of [hexacyanoferrate(III)] (Table 1). The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in [benzoin] (Table 2), indicating the first order reaction with respect to benzoin. The oxidation rate of benzoin is directly proportional to [alkali] (Table 3) and hence the order in latter is unity. The rate constant increases with the increase in [catalyst]. The values of k_0 [OsO_4] show fairly concordant values of all concentrations of the catalyst (Table 4)

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)]
[Benzoin] = 0.05 M; [OH⁻] = 0.01 M; [OsO_4] = 2.5×10^{-3} M;
 μ = 0.3 M; Solvent: 30% t-butanol (v/v);
Temp. = 30°

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] $\times 10^3$ M	k_0 $\times 10_4$ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
1.0	19.20
2.0	19.20
4.0	19.00
6.0	19.00
8.0	18.78
10.0	18.50

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [BENZOIN]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 0.002 M; [OsO₄] = 2.5 × 10⁻⁵ M; [OH⁻] = 0.01 M; μ = 0.3 M; Solvent: 30% t-butanol (v/v); Temp = 30°

[Benzoin] × 10 ³ M	k _o × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k _o , min ⁻¹ [Benzoin]
1.0	3.85	0.385
2.0	7.60	0.380
4.0	15.25	0.386
5.0	19.20	0.384
8.0	30.50	0.381
10.0	38.50	0.385

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [OH⁻]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 0.002 M; [Benzoin] = 0.02 M; [OsO₄] = 2.5 × 10⁻⁵ M; μ = 0.3 M; Solvent: 30% t-butanol (v/v), Temp = 35°

[OH ⁻] × 10 ³ M	k _o × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k _o , min [OH ⁻]
1.0	7.60	0.76
2.0	15.40	0.77
4.0	31.20	0.78
6.0	46.20	0.77
8.0	60.00	0.75
10.0	77.00	0.77

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [OsO₄]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 0.002 M; [Benzoin] = 0.02 M; [OH⁻] = 0.01 M; μ = 0.3 M; Solvent: t-butanol (v/v); Temp = 30°

[OsO ₄] × 10 ³ M	k _o × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k _o × 10 ⁻³ min ⁻¹ [OsO ₄]
1.0	2.8	0.28
1.5	4.35	0.29
2.5	7.60	0.30
3.5	10.85	0.31
5.0	15.10	0.31
6.0	19.20	0.32
7.0	23.80	0.34
10.0	33.00	0.33
12.0	38.40	0.32
14.0	42.00	0.30
15.0	45.00	0.30

Effect of ionic strength: The rate of reaction increases with the increase in ionic strength of the medium and a plot of log k_o vs √μ is linear, indicating an ion-ion interaction. Added ferrocyanide showed no effect on the rate of oxidation.

Solvent effect: The decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium decreases the rate constant. The plot of log k_o vs reciprocal of the dielectric constant of the medium is linear, which provides an additional evidence in favour of ion-ion reaction.

Effect of substituents on rate: The rate data of substituted benzoin at different temperatures have also been recorded in Table 5. Arrhenius equation has been found to be valid within the temperature range studied. The observed reactivity of the substituted benzoin confirms to the following order,

It is evident from the order of reactivity that the rate increases by the electron-releasing substituents on the benzene nucleus directly attached to the keto group and retarded by the electron-attracting groups. The logarithm of the rate constants at 35° correlate well with σ⁺ values⁵. The value of ρ⁺ is -1.15. A similar correlation between log k_o and σ⁺ has been observed earlier⁶ for the dichromate oxidation of benzoin. The above order of reactivity is in agreement with the negative value of ρ⁺. A common mechanism is envisaged for the substituted benzoin as the free energy of activation values are of same order of magnitude.

Isokinetic relationship: A linear relationship between the entropy of activation (ΔS[‡]) and the enthalpy of activation (ΔH[‡]) has been observed for the oxidation of benzoin⁷. The data can be fitted in the equation,

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_o^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$$

where, ΔH[‡] = 21.15 kcal mol⁻¹ and β = 330 K. The linear relationship shown by the majority of the substituted benzoin indicates that the same mechanism operates in all the cases⁸.

Mechanism: The osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of benzoin by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) is characterised by the following: (i) the reaction rate is independent of initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) but proportional to the concentration of benzoin, alkali and osmium tetroxide, (ii) the reaction rate decreases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the solvent but increases with the increase in ionic strength of the medium, (iii) the entropy of activation is found to be negative and a negative ρ⁺ value

TABLE 5—REACTION RATES AND ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR ALKALINE HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) OXIDATION OF BENZOIN IN t-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURE

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 0.002 M; [Substrate] = 0.02 M; [OH⁻] = 0.01 M; [OsO₄] = 2.5 × 10⁻⁵ M; μ = 0.3 M; Solvent: 30% t-butanol (v/v); Temp = 30°

Substrate	k _o × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹			E kcal mol ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] e.u.	ΔH [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹
	30°	35°	40°			
4-OCH ₃	15.50	25.80	36.70	16.50	14.31	15.88
4-CH ₃	12.80	21.70	32.50	17.40	11.71	16.78
H	7.60	12.80	20.50	18.20	10.17	17.58
4-Cl	6.20	10.60	16.30	19.20	7.29	18.58
2,2'-dinitro	5.50	8.80	12.80	19.80	5.71	19.18

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